

Palm Tree Resort and Hotel Subic Bay: Facilities & Services

Castaway's Bar

Enjoy the beautiful view while catching sunrays on the [Palm Tree Resort](#) top bar. Features glorious views of scenic shoreline and idyllic sunsets, island-inspired furnishings and a spirit of casual elegance. Bathed in natural light, the gentle hues of nature are infused in every surrounding. It is just the beginning of the refined amenities that will fill your stay with rare pleasures.

The Palm Tree Restaurant

Daily Specials (From 12NN-10PM):

MONDAY

-BBQ

TUESDAY

-Indian Curry Night

WEDNESDAY

-BBQ

THURSDAY

-Mongolian BBQ

FRIDAY

-BBQ

SATURDAY

-BBQ

SUNDAY

-Roast Carvery

Amenities

-PoolBar

-Beach

-Parking Area

-Watersports (upon request)

-Other Services

-Laundry & Ironing

-Room Services

-Tour arrangements

-Golf

-Go-cart

-Horse Back Riding

-Ocean Adventure / Zoobic Safari

-Airport and City transfer

Free parking available 24/7

-On call massage

-Business

-Facsimile

-Wi-Fi access available in every room and throughout the area.

Live Band

-Wednesdays, Fridays and Saturdays

-7PM, until Late

Drinks

Imported Beers

-Strongbow, Heineken, Guinness, Leffee, Murphy's, Konig Ludwig, Budweiser

Local Drink

-Tanduary Ice, Vodka Ice, Vodka Cruiser

Large Selection of Assorted Wines

-Draught

-Php 40

-SMB/SML

-PHP 50